

IMPROVEMENT OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF USED METHYLETHANOLAMINE (MDEA) AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF PURIFICATION METHODS

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Abstract. A 30% aqueous solution of spent methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) can be regenerated and reused for gas treatment, while its residual components can serve as secondary raw materials in other industrial applications.

Keywords: purified amine, MDEA, secondary row materials, surface tension

Аннотация. 30% водный раствор отработанного метилдиэтанолamina (МДЭА) можно регенерировать и повторно использовать для очистки газа, в то время как его остаточные компоненты могут служить вторичным сырьем в других промышленных применениях.

Ключевые слова: очищенный амин, МДЭА, вторичные материалы.

Annatatsiya. Ishlatilgan metil dietanolaminning (MDEA) 30% suvli eritmasi qayta tiklanishi va gazni qayta ishlash uchun qayta ishlatilishi mumkin, uning qoldiq komponentlari esa boshqa sanoat ilovalarida ikkilamchi xom ashyo sifatida xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: tozalangan amin, MDEA, ikkilamchi homashyo.

Introduction. Methylethanolamine, also known as N-methyl diethanolamine, is commonly an organic compound formulated MDEA, $\text{CH}_3\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{OH})_2$. It is a colorless liquid that has the smell of ammonia. Water is mixed with ethanol and benzene. Tertiary amine, it is widely used as a sweetening agent in chemical, refinery, synthesis gas production, and natural gas. Similar compounds are monoethanolamine (MEA), primary amine, and diethanolamine (DEA), a secondary amine, both used to treat amine gas. The defining feature of MDEA compared to these other amines is its ability to preferentially remove H_2S (and draw CO_2) from sour gas streams. [1]

The main peaks in the IR spectrum of $(\text{HOCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NCH}_3$ are peaks caused by valence and deformation vibrations of methylene groups and OH, C–N and C–O vibrations. For example, the intense peak in the high frequency region (3359 cm^{-1}) was caused by the valence vibrations of OH groups. C–O and C–N absorption bands are observed in the region of 1034 and 1201 cm^{-1} , respectively. Peaks characteristic of valence vibrations of the methylene group are observed at $2800 - 3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and peaks characteristic of deformational vibrations are observed at $1200 - 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $400 - 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 2. IR spectrum of pure $(\text{HOCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NCH}_3$. Quantitative analysis of the component $(\text{HOCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NCH}_3$ showed the presence of a small amount of $(\text{HOCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NCH}_3$. It is known that piperidine is formed as a result of reaction of two $(\text{HOCH}_2\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NCH}_3$ under solid conditions.

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